

Citizen Science Institutional Change Through BESCPOC Implementations

Report on Achievements in the Five Participating Institutions

Prepared for: LibOCS, an ERASMUS+ Project

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Project Number: 2021-1-EE01-KA220-HED-000031125

Project Acronym: LibOCS

Project Title: University libraries strengthening the academia-society connection through citizen science in the Baltics

This project is funded under the Erasmus+ KA2 Strategic Partnerships program.

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	2
List of acronyms	3
Executive Summary	4
Purpose of the report and its structure	6
Structure of the Report	6
Introduction	7
Background information on the LibOCS project	7
Overview of the BESPOC model and its relevance to LibOCS's objectives.	8
Implementation methodology	9
Institutional Change through BESPOC: An Overview	11
BESPOC Model and Institutional Change	11
Achievements in the Participating Institutions	12
University of Tartu	12
University of Latvia	14
Kaunas University of Technology	15
Vytautas Magnus University	17
Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech)	18
Cross-institutional Analysis	19
Recommendations	22
References	24

List of acronyms

BESPOC - Broad Engagement in Science, Point of Contact

CRIS - Current Research Information System

CS - Citizen Science

EE - Country Code for Estonia

ETIS - Estonian Research Portal

GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation

HEIs - Higher Education Institutions

HSS - Humanities and Social Sciences

KTU - Kaunas University of Technology

LERU - League of European Research Universities

LibOCS - Project Acronym (stands for Libraries for Open and Citizen Science)

LT - Country Code for Lithuania

UL - University of Latvia

LV - Country Code for Latvia

OS - Open Science

PR1, PR2, PR3, PR5, PR6 - Work packages specific to LibOCS Project

TalTech - Tallinn University of Technology

UT - University of Tartu

VMU - Vytautas Magnus University

Executive Summary

This report presents insights and analyses from the implementation of the BESPOC model (Broad Engagement in Science, Point of Contact) across five Baltic Higher Education Institutions (HEIs): University of Tartu (UT), Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech), University of Latvia (UL), Vytautas Magnus University (VMU), and Kaunas University of Technology (KTU). The implementation was made possible by LibOCS, an EU-funded ERASMUS+ project.

The goal of implementing the BESPOC model is to systematically support a robust connection between academia and society by integrating public engagement and citizen science (CS) into university services, thereby promoting public participation in scientific research and scientific literacy to the large public. It is recommended for universities to increase their presence in society through research, thus promoting solid values and evidence-based thinking at all levels of society.

Key observations from implementation process:

- The 5 universities are at different stages of BESPOC implementation, ranging from initial discussions and planning phases at UT, TalTech, and VMU, to more advanced stages of stakeholder engagement, project initiation, and the establishment of guidelines for CS projects at UL and KTU.
- LU and KTU have experienced significant institutional changes as a direct result of BESPOC implementation, including the approval of guidelines for CS projects and the initiation of collaborative partnerships to support CS activities.
- Common challenges across the HEIs include engaging stakeholders, integrating the BESPOC model into existing structures, and securing support for citizen science activities.

Recommendations

- Enhancing academia-society cooperation through strategies such as developing targeted communication plans, expanding public outreach and education, leveraging digital platforms, and institutionalising CS within university curricula.
- Further customisation of the BESPOC service at each institution: e.g. strengthening support and resources for implementation, promoting inter-institutional collaboration, and addressing legal and ethical considerations.

Reflection on Impact

The introduction of the BESPOC model has initiated a shift towards recognising the importance of CS in academia, albeit with varying degrees of impact across the participating HEIs. Institutions like UL and KTU have made notable progress, setting examples for integrating CS into their operations and fostering a culture that values public engagement in scientific endeavours.

Conclusion

The implementation of the BESPOC model across LibOCS project HEIs marks a clear step towards bridging the gap between academia and society through CS. Despite facing challenges and being at different stages of implementation, the collective efforts of these institutions show a commitment to

support CS for societal benefit. Continued focus on strategic planning, overcoming challenges, and stakeholder engagement will be essential elements for realising the full potential of these initiatives in strengthening the academia-society cooperation.

Purpose of the report and its structure

The primary objective of this report is to document the progress and achievements of each participating university in the LibOCS project up to the present moment. This assessment focuses on various critical dimensions, including the level of implementation of the BESPOC model, the necessary further steps to continue advancing in this initiative, and the tangible effects observed as a result of these efforts. Through a detailed analysis, this report aims to provide a comprehensive overview of how each partner institution has navigated the challenges and opportunities presented by the integration of CS within their academic framework, pursuant to the broader objectives of the LibOCS project.

The importance of this evaluation lies in its potential to guide future strategies and actions, rather than in its capacity to measure progress. By identifying successful practices, areas requiring additional attention, and the overall impact of the project to date, the report serves as a foundational tool for both continued improvement and strategic planning. Moreover, it seeks to contribute to the broader discourse on CS by sharing insights and lessons learned with the global academic and research community, thereby enriching the collective understanding and implementation of these practices.

Thus, the purpose of this report is not to compare and rank the outcomes of the BESPOC implementations across the five participating universities. Instead, we acknowledge the unique circumstances, priorities, research fields, and temporal contexts of each institution. The essence of BESPOC implementation through the LibOCS project is rooted in nurturing a collaborative spirit rather than competition. It aims to cultivate an environment of mutual encouragement, exchange of practices, and profound practical dialogue. This approach ensures that each university's effort in integrating citizen science is valued for its contributions to the collective learning and advancement of the academic community.

Structure of the Report

The structure of this report is designed to facilitate a clear, comprehensive, and accessible presentation of findings, organised as follows:

1. The introduction provides background information on the LibOCS project, a description of the BESPOC model and its relevance, and outlines the purpose of this report. This section sets the stage for the detailed analysis that follows.
2. The “Implementation Methodology” part explains the approach and methods used to implement BESPOC at each participating institution, according to the LibOCS project plan.
3. This report dedicates a separate part that highlights a brief overview to the institutional changes through BESPOC implementation.
4. A section looks into the achievements within participating institutions which constitutes the core of the report, presenting a detailed account of the progress and successes at each university. This section is subdivided into segments per institution, covering:
 - a. Implementation process and key milestones
 - b. Specific institutional changes observed - highlighting the changes and developments observed within partner institutions as a result of the project.
 - c. Impact assessment - evaluates the effects of these changes, both within the institutions and in the broader context of their engagement with CS.
 - d. Estimated level of implementation and necessary further steps. This segment assesses the current state of implementation and outlines the planned steps for the next 6, 12, and 24 months.

5. The cross-institutional analysis offers a way to identify common challenges, shared successes, and lessons learned, facilitating a synthesis of insights that can guide future initiatives.
6. Our recommendations propose actionable steps for each HEI, as well as for the project as a whole, to enhance the integration of CS practices in their regular activities.

Introduction

Background information on the LibOCS project

Citizen science, a collaborative approach to science marking the intersection of public participation and scientific research, is gaining recognition across Europe for its ability to tackle scientific challenges in a societal context. Acknowledged by the European Union for its potential to enhance scientific and policy landscapes, citizen science initiatives are increasingly integrated into broader frameworks. Yet, the degree of integration into academic and community ecosystems varies on countries, regions, institutions and disciplines.

The BESPOC Model addresses the need for a whole-organisation support service for CS at research organisations. Rooted in a 2016 League of European Research Universities' (LERU) recommendation and evolving from the BESPOC Prototype, it aims to unlock Citizen Science's potential to meet Open Science (OS) challenges at the institutional level, emphasizing the importance of making research accessible and socially beneficial. Despite the Baltic states' progress in OS, there's still an evident gap in fully leveraging CS, highlighting an ongoing effort to merge CS with open science practices.

The LibOCS project aims to bridge this disparity, focusing on mainstreaming CS in the Baltic countries (Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania), known for their OS commitment. The project's goal is to unlock CS's potential, making it accessible and synergised with OS to enrich the academic environment. By charting CS and OS implementations' progress, sharing best practices, and engaging diverse public groups, LibOCS seeks to reinvigorate the academia-society relationship.

Structured around five objectives, each linked to a specific Project Result (PR), LibOCS aims to¹:

1. map drivers and barriers of civic engagement in OS and share in-depth insights on the role academic libraries can play in CS activities in the region.
2. maintain a dialogue and action plan among Higher Education teaching/research staff and librarians in the Baltic states, collaborating on CSproject that involves any volunteer. It will provide an opportunity to focus strategically on the position of libraries in contemporary information societies.
3. conduct LibOCS training to improve the CS and OS skills of academic and library personnel in the Baltics.
4. create institutional change through testing and implementing a CS single point of contact in participating LibOCS universities.
5. create an Open Access toolkit for librarians on the topic of CS with all tools available as open educational resources (OER), open to (re-)use, and repurposing.

¹ <https://www.libocs.ut.ee/>

Targeting university library staff, academic staff at HEIs, and the general public, LibOCS, driven by a consortium of five HEIs and partners like Web2Learn and Immer Besser GmbH, made already notable progress in connecting academia with society in the Baltic region.

The implementation of the BESPOC model across the five Baltic HEIs promises multiple benefits. It aims to create a structured interface for streamlined actions and information dissemination related to CS initiatives. When fully implemented, this approach is expected to facilitate collaboration, break down barriers, enhance efficiency, and integrate CS with other OS activities. Moreover, by supporting CS projects transparently and efficiently, the BESPOC model is set to build trust, encourage community participation, augment institutions' capacity to manage CS projects effectively, and position the LibOCS HEIs as leaders in the European citizen science landscape.

Overview of the BESPOC model and its relevance to LibOCS's objectives.

The BESPOC model represents a comprehensive approach designed to enhance public engagement and support citizen science initiatives within universities and research organizations. BESPOC is aligned with the LERU recommendations and the LIBER Citizen Science Working Group, advocating for a structured and supportive environment for citizen science.

Modules of BESPOC

- **Policy & Development Plans (P&D-CS):** This module is focused on the development and periodic updating of policies specific to citizen science, aiming to institutionalize these practices within academic settings. It ensures the effective communication and engagement of these policies across the institution.
- **Activities Portal (AP):** Acting as a central hub, the Activities Portal facilitates the transformation of policies into actionable projects and campaigns. It supports project engagement, dissemination, and collaboration, serving as a vital resource for citizen science endeavors.
- **Partnership Frameworks (PFs):** BESPOC emphasises establishing collaborative relationships with various stakeholders, outlining the structure, roles, responsibilities, and objectives of these partnerships. This framework enhances the impact of citizen science both in academia and in broader society.
- **Templates for Citizen Science Projects (TCSP):** Providing essential resources for initiating and executing CS projects, this module includes consent forms, data collection sheets, and safety protocols to aid in ethical compliance and effective communication.
- **Specific Citizen Science Communication (SCSC):** Tailored to address the unique challenges of communicating complex research to non-professionals, this module promotes accessibility, engagement, and two-way communication, fostering transparency and adherence to OS principles.
- **Research Management & Administration Connector (RMA-C):** This connector integrates CS activities with existing research management systems, facilitating efficient workflows, policy integration, and enhanced support for citizen science projects within the institution.
- **Gateway to Society (GtS):** Empowering citizens to contribute to shaping research priorities and ensuring research findings inform policymaking, GtS strengthens the connections between research activities and decision-making processes.

- **Legal & Safety Office Connector (LS-C):** Ensuring legal and safety compliance is paramount in citizen science projects. This module facilitates understanding and responses to legal and safety matters, safeguarding participants, researchers, and the institution.
- **Communities Builder (CB):** Focused on cultivating sustainable communities around citizen science projects, CB supports the development of Communities of Interest, Knowledge, and Practice, encouraging personal and collective growth within these communities.

The implementation process

The BESPOC model highlights the critical importance of policy development, community engagement, legal compliance, and the effective management of citizen science projects, serving as a guideline for research organizations striving for a more inclusive, collaborative, and impactful research environment.

The BESPOC model is offered as a consultancy service, providing tailored guidance and support for establishing a citizen science point of contact. While the BESPOC Prototype is available open access, the comprehensive BESPOC Model aids institutions in promoting citizen science, facilitating collaboration, and ensuring transparency and effective communication in research projects. It supports cross-departmental collaboration, staff and infrastructure development, and active community engagement in research.

The BESPOC model is a dynamic and practical approach to integrating citizen science into academic and research institutions in a structured and holistic way. Its implementation always take into consideration existing CS practices, initiatives, and projects. Aligned with this, it's best implemented when acknowledging and working with existing groups of researchers or librarians practicing or supporting citizen science.

Implementation methodology

Our implementation methodology was designed to integrate the BESPOC model within each participating university by following the LibOCS project plan and by acknowledging the particular context for each institution. The process was designed to ensure a comprehensive and effective adoption of citizen science practices at a pace that allows nurturing a genuine collaborative spirit among all stakeholders involved.

Spanning pre-implementation consultations, priority setting, module implementation, diverse stakeholder engagement, and the utilization of collaborative tools, this methodology facilitated a nuanced understanding and execution of the BESPOC model.

Pre-Implementation Consultation and Analysis

Initially, each participating HEI engaged in two pre-consultation workshops and individualized sessions, totaling ten across all institutions. These preliminary interactions were necessary for setting the groundwork for the project, allowing for an initial assessment of each institution's readiness, needs, and expectations regarding the BESPOC model implementation. The findings and insights from these consultations were compiled into a report titled "Analysis Report And Initial Recommendations (subtitle: Pre-implementation consultation at Baltic HEIs)", representing the 26th milestone of the LibOCS Project.

This document served as a foundational resource for guiding subsequent phases of the project, outlining initial recommendations and strategic priorities tailored to each HEI.

Priority Setting and Custom Workshops

Following the pre-implementation analysis, each HEI independently determined their priorities concerning the BESPOC modules they wished to implement first. This decision-making process led to the selection of 3-4 priority modules per institution, which formed the basis for the next phase of tailored workshops and consultations. These sessions were designed to address the specific needs and contexts of each university, facilitating a focused approach to implementing the selected BESPOC modules.

Comprehensive Module Implementation

After the initial phase of targeted consultation and workshop delivery on the priority modules, the project expanded to cover all nine BESPOC modules. This comprehensive phase involved delivering workshops to all HEIs, aimed at implementing the remaining BESPOC modules and ensuring a holistic integration of the model across institutional frameworks. The workshops were instrumental in providing detailed guidance and support for each module's application within the unique contexts of the participating universities.

Diverse Participant Recruitment

A critical but also difficult aspect of the methodology was the recruitment of a diverse group of participants for the implementation workshops and consultations. Each HEI assembled teams comprising researchers, librarians, research managers and administrators, university managers (a.g. the vice-rector level), and students. This multi-perspective approach ensured that the implementation of the BESPOC model was informed by a wide range of insights and expertise, fostering a more inclusive and representative process.

Collaborative Tools and Communication Platforms

To facilitate collaboration, documentation, and communication throughout the project, a suite of digital tools was employed. Google Drive, Google Docs, Google Forms, and Google Calendar were used for collaborative document management, scheduling, and feedback collection. These tools allowed for real-time collaboration, efficient document sharing, and streamlined project management across all participating institutions.

For communication and meeting preservation, Zoom was the primary platform used for virtual workshops, consultations, and discussions. Vimeo served as the repository for recorded sessions, enabling participants to access and review workshops and presentations at their convenience. This approach ensured that all project stakeholders remained engaged and informed, regardless of geographical location or scheduling constraints.

Analytical Framework

The analytical component was structured around evaluating the implementation processes, key milestones achieved, specific institutional changes observed, and the impact of these changes. This evaluation drew on qualitative and quantitative data collected through workshops, consultations, and collaborative tools, providing a nuanced understanding of each HEI's progress and achievements in integrating the BESPOC model.

Institutional Change through BESPOC: An Overview

The evolution of citizen science within universities signifies a profound shift towards more inclusive, participatory forms of scientific inquiry and research. This shift is buoyed by European Union (EU) research programs that explicitly incorporate citizen science, recognizing its potential to foster innovation, and societal engagement, and address complex challenges. Programs like Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe exemplify this, highlighting a systemic push towards integrating citizen science within academic and research frameworks. The expectation is clear: HEIs are to adapt by developing supportive policies, building capacities for citizen science projects, enhancing infrastructures, and revising ethical and legal frameworks to accommodate this new paradigm of public engagement in science. EU-funded projects, such as EU-Citizen.Science², CSI-COP³, OpenLitterMap⁴, or Time4CS⁵, showcase successful integration and the tangible societal impacts of citizen science, ranging from environmental monitoring to enhancing public engagement with research. These projects advance scientific knowledge while at the same time growing a sense of community and public empowerment, aligning with the EU's broader open science and participatory research agendas.

Furthermore, the current global context, where democracies face challenges from misinformation and manipulation, underscores the importance of citizen science. By directly involving the public in the scientific process, citizen science serves as a necessary avenue for disseminating trustworthy information, fostering critical thinking, and enhancing public understanding and trust in science. This participatory approach is vital for sustaining democracies, combating misinformation, and ensuring that science remains a collaborative, inclusive endeavour that benefits society as a whole.

BESPOC Model and Institutional Change

The BESPOC model, with its comprehensive modules ranging from Policy & Development Plans to Communities Builder, provides a structured framework for universities and research organizations to navigate and implement these expected institutional changes. By addressing specific aspects of citizen science, from project initiation and public engagement to ethical compliance and legal considerations, BESPOC contributes to the EU's vision for academic engagement, science participation and citizen science. It operationalizes one of the most important recommendations outlined in the LERU's Advice Paper No. 20 (October 2016)⁶, which - overall - emphasizes the importance of institutional support, open science standards, community management, and ethical considerations in citizen science projects. The particular recommendation that the BESPOC model is turning into practice is the 2nd recommendation for institutions which reads "Consider creating, where viable, a single point of contact for citizen science within the institution, to advise scientists and ensure liaison with national and regional citizen science initiatives". The BESPOC model exemplifies a proactive response to this call for greater public participation in science, not only aligning with LERU's recommendations for universities to recognize and support citizen science (create centralized points of contact), but going beyond LERU's recommendations and creating a university-supported service for citizen science initiatives, activities and projects. Furthermore, it ensures compliance with ethical and open science standards. This model serves as a blueprint for modern universities aiming to foster a culture of participatory research and

² <https://eu-citizen.science/>

³ <https://csi-cop.eu/>

⁴ <https://openlittermap.com/>

⁵ <https://www.time4cs.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.leru.org/publications/citizen-science-at-universities-trends-guidelines-and-recommendations>

public engagement, thus facilitating institutional change that embraces the societal and educational benefits of citizen science.

While the integration of the BESPOC model within universities represents an example of recommendation-turned-practice, the 2016 Advice Paper contains other actionable guidelines and policy recommendations provided by LERU for advancing citizen science. These include recognizing the value of citizen science, ensuring proper organizational structures, promoting open science practices, and addressing ethical and legal issues. Hence, the BESPOC model expands from “a single point of contact” on a comprehensive institutional support and cross-departmental collaboration. It mirrors LERU's call for universities to adapt their policies, infrastructure, and evaluation systems to include and support citizen science activities.

We strongly believe that by adopting the BESPOC model and aligning with LERU's recommendations, universities can effectively navigate the complexities of institutional change required for the successful integration of citizen science. This will enhance their research and educational missions and it will also contribute to a more informed, engaged, and democratic society. This is the path for an institutional change that will benefit Europe, research at large and democratic societies.

Achievements in the Participating Institutions

This section provides details on the following areas of the practical BESPOC implementation within the LibOCS project: 1) implementation process and key milestones, 2) overview of specific institutional changes observed, 3) impact assessment, and 4) challenges and future steps before drawing 5) conclusions.

University of Tartu

Implementation Process and Key Milestones

The implementation of the BESPOC model at the University of Tartu (UT) is scheduled from 2023 to 2025, marking a strategic period for embedding citizen science (CS) deeper into the university's structure and operational philosophy. Initial stages have focused on understanding the BESPOC model, engaging in consultations with various stakeholders, developing a comprehensive framework for CS, and initiating the planning process. These steps represent foundational elements that have set the stage for further integration and development of CS projects within the institution.

Institutional Changes Observed

One of the most significant changes observed as a result of implementing the BESPOC model has been the enhanced connection of the UT library with CS activities, as recognized by university stakeholders. This development marks a shift in perception, placing the library at the core of CS initiatives within the university. It signifies an institutional recognition of the library's value and potential role in supporting and - possibly - initiating CS projects, thus broadening the scope of its contribution to academic and societal engagement.

Impact Assessment

The immediate impact of the BESPOC model implementation at UT, while modest in its initial stages, has been positive. The library's stature among university stakeholders has notably increased, indicating a growing acknowledgement of its important role in supporting and advancing CS initiatives. However, actual involvement in CS activities from the broader university community remains minimal at this early phase. Despite this, there are promising signs of increased interest and potential collaborations in the CS area, as stakeholders have begun to seek cooperation with the library on CS-related projects.

Notable initiatives stemming from the BESPOC model's introduction include the beginning of mapping CS projects at UT and the planning to publish CS project templates on the Estonian open science website maintained by the university. These steps are critical for laying the groundwork for a more structured and visible CS environment within the university.

In terms of measurable outcomes, plans are underway to organize an event aimed at raising awareness about CS, as a direct result of the BESPOC model's implementation. This event, along with the creation and dissemination of CS project templates and checklists, is part of the immediate next steps planned for the upcoming 6 months. Looking further ahead, into the next 12 and 24 months, the library aims to launch its own CS project and continue discussions with the Grant Office (BESPOC's RMA-C module) on providing support for university CS projects, indicating a strategic approach to deepening and expanding the implementation of the BESPOC model.

Challenges and Future Steps

Despite the positive developments, UT has encountered challenges, particularly in engaging and motivating stakeholders to participate in and take further steps after the initial BESPOC consultations. Addressing these challenges involved identifying and engaging interested individuals, find the right dialogue practice and the most fitting rhetoric, but also fostering a willingness to advance CS initiatives.

The university has rated its current level of BESPOC model implementation at a 2 on a scale of 1 to 10, acknowledging that they are just starting this ambitious journey. The next immediate steps include creating and publishing templates and checklists for CS projects and mapping existing CS projects within UT, with an emphasis on addressing legal questions around CS projects, securing resources, and obtaining necessary funding for effective implementation.

Conclusion

The University of Tartu is at the initial stages of implementing the BESPOC model, with a focused approach on embedding CS into its institutional framework. Despite facing challenges related to stakeholder engagement and resource limitations, there is a strong commitment to advancing CS initiatives, underscored by strategic planning and the development of supportive tools and events. As UT continues to navigate the complexities of integrating the BESPOC model, its journey unveils valuable insights into the process of institutional change and the potential of libraries as central figures in the promotion and support of citizen science.

University of Latvia

Implementation Process and Key Milestones

The University of Latvia (UL) embarked on its journey to integrate the BESPOC model from June 2023, with a projected timeline extending to December 2024. Key milestones have included conducting pre-implementation consultations, analyzing current CS practices within UL and the broader Latvian context, and organizing workshops for stakeholder feedback on the BESPOC model. Additionally, UL has participated in drafting significant documents, such as "[BESPOC Implementation at Baltic Universities: A LibOCS Analysis Report and Initial Recommendations](#)" and "Implementing Citizen Science Activities in Baltic University Libraries: On the Road to a Citizen Science Hub."

The UL team rates the LibOCS Workshops and Consultancy provided by Immer Besser with a perfect score of 10, indicating high satisfaction with the support received. This feedback underscores the importance of patience, creativity, and time in navigating the complexities of BESPOC model integration and achieving long-term cultural change within the university and society at large.

Institutional Changes Observed

The implementation process has already begun to reshape perceptions of the Library at UL, highlighting its potential to support CS activities effectively. Notably, productive collaborations have been established with two departments within UL, fostering an environment conducive to CS engagement and support.

Impact Assessment

The introduction of the BESPOC model has catalyzed a reevaluation of CS support development, allowing for a more nuanced approach to service development. The library has become an active platform for discussing civic engagement in research, evidenced by its role in organizing conference and other events that gather stakeholders and interested parties to exchange experiences in CS. Successful cooperation with the Citizen Science Ambassador of the ECS project in Latvia has also been initiated. Those who are engaged and interested in Citizen Science at the University of Latvia have raised the question of the need to organize regular meetings. Although specific CS projects directly benefitting from the BESPOC model are yet to grow, the library's evolving role as a CS advocate and supporter is evident.

Immediate impacts of the BESPOC model implementation include increased engagement with CS implementers and an invitation for the library to join a CS-related project. Despite facing uncertainties due to structural consolidations within LU, the library's active involvement in CS discussions and the organization of conferences demonstrate its commitment to strengthening the academia-society connection. The UL Library, with its activities, also positions itself as a leader in promoting CS initiative and knowledge regarding cooperation of society, researchers and librarians in research in the librarian society of Latvia.

Challenges and Future Steps

Challenges such as fragmented information on civic engagement and structural consolidation processes at UL have been addressed through diligent information gathering and the library's proactive development of a CS support service. These efforts aim to enhance cooperation across UL departments and with external stakeholders.

In the next 6 months, UL plans to focus on implementing a solution for a "Gateway to Society" (a BESPOC module), identifying and engaging with potential CS projects, and promoting the

eu-citizen.science platform as a resource for CS projects. Looking further ahead, UL aims to initiate its own CS project and establish an annual tradition of hosting a conference or forum to foster community engagement in CS.

The effective implementation of the BESPOC model at UL requires reinforcement of the university's Open Science Policy with a robust strategy, skill enhancement and team expansion within the library, and continuous advocacy for the development of CS support services amid ongoing structural changes. The high turnover of qualified personnel also presents a challenge to sustaining momentum in BESPOC model implementation.

Conclusion

The University of Latvia's engagement with the BESPOC model marks a notable step towards embedding CS into its institutional framework and culture. Despite challenges, the proactive efforts to establish the library as a central figure in CS support, coupled with strategic planning for future initiatives, reflect a deep commitment to leveraging CS for enhancing the academia-society connection. As UL continues this transformative initiative, the lessons learned and the foundations laid promise to yield significant benefits for the university and its broader community.

Kaunas University of Technology

Implementation Process and Key Milestones

The process of integrating the BESPOC model at Kaunas University of Technology (KTU) began in June 2023 with two consultations between the BESPOC consultant and the KTU Library team. These initial consultations focused on understanding KTU's research infrastructure, identifying potential implementation partners within the university, and determining the necessary departments to be involved. From September to November 2023, KTU Library sought out departments and professionals within the university to discuss the BESPOC implementation perspectives at an institutional level. This was followed by the organization of two workshops from November to December 2023, aimed at research administrators, researchers, and Doctoral School members, to discuss the priorities of Citizen Science (CS) activities implementation at KTU, selecting four modules as most important, with Gateway to Society highlighted as the primary focus. The period from December 2023 to January 2024 was dedicated to analyzing the Gateway to Society module, Activities portal, Community Builder, and Specific CS communication, culminating in a meeting with the Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts, and Humanities (SHMF) researchers group to delineate activities for implementing BESPOC. By January 2024, a plan for BESPOC modules implementation at KTU Library for the year was prepared, alongside a project application for the support and development of BESPOC activities. In March 2024, guidelines for the initiation and conduct of CS projects were approved at KTU.

Key Milestones Achieved

The collaboration with the researcher group from KTU's Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts, and Humanities (SHMF) led to the establishment of a CS center. The initiative of the SHMF researchers' group has been essential, with the library taking responsibility for updating the CS webpage and disseminating information to the university community and other stakeholders. Furthermore, collaboration with public

libraries has begun to expand the network of CS-skilled librarians and reach diverse societal groups potentially interested in CS.

The LibOCS Workshops and Consultancy regarding the BESPOC offered by Immer Besser were rated very highly at 10 out of 10.

Institutional Changes Observed

The approval of "Guidelines for the Initiation and Conduct of Citizen Science Projects" (<https://biblioteka.ktu.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/38/2024/03/KTU-pilieciu-mokslo-projektu-inicijavimo-i-vykdyimo-gaires.pdf>) at KTU marks a significant step towards enhancing CS projects at the university. This development, alongside increased familiarity of the university's top management with CS activities and the expansion of CS activities beyond the university through involvement in the ECIU University network and FOR-EU Library Group activities, highlights the evolving institutional approach to CS.

The KTU Library established a collaboration with the Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts, and Humanities (SHMF) researcher group, leading to the creation of a CS center. This initiative positioned the library as responsible for updating the CS webpage and disseminating information within the university and to other stakeholders. Additionally, KTU initiated collaboration with public libraries to broaden the network of CS-knowledgeable librarians and reach more diverse societal groups.

While specific projects directly initiated through the BESPOC model are pending evaluation, a project application for the development of the Citizen Science Centre has been prepared in collaboration with SHMF. Additionally, an application to a new project with international partners focusing on citizen engagement has been submitted, with the evaluation of these applications still awaited.

Impact Assessment

Although still in the development phase, the introduction of the BESPOC model at KTU has led to the library being recognized as a central hub for the advocacy and support of CS within the university.

The KTU Library has become a leading ambassador for CS at the university, disseminating information about CS at the national level and, as mentioned before, participating in international university networks like ECIU and FOR-EU Library Group.

KTU rates its current level of BESPOC model implementation at 6 out of 10. This rating considers the discussions with top management about establishing BESPOC, the partnership established with SHMF for joint CS activities, the approval and dissemination of CS project guidelines, the operation of a CS information portal, and the organization of workshops and training on CS for various stakeholder groups.

Challenges and Future Steps

Finding partners for supporting CS activities and establishing a BESPOC at KTU posed significant challenges, along with introducing university administration to the benefits and potential of CS. Efforts to convene stakeholders for CS seminars and discussions also faced hurdles. These challenges were addressed through meetings with representatives from various scientific departments and projects, which facilitated a better understanding of the benefits of CS and encouraged dialogue.

Moving forward, KTU plans to develop the Activities Portal, update CS project information, and collaborate with public libraries to present CS activities to the public.

In the next six months, KTU plans to develop the Activities Portal by updating information about CS for the university community and the public, and update the list of CS projects conducted at KTU.

Collaboration with public libraries aims to make connections with society by presenting CS activities at events organized in collaboration with a public library. The long-term plan includes improving existing activities, informing, and encouraging the university's academic community to initiate projects involving the public.

Conclusion

KTU's journey toward implementing the BESPOC model highlights the importance of strategic collaboration, especially between the Faculty and Library, in strengthening the role of CS within the university. Through deliberate discussions, partnership building, and the establishment of CS guidelines, KTU has taken significant steps toward embedding a culture of citizen science. While still in the early stages, KTU's efforts demonstrate a commitment to advancing CS activities and fostering a greater connection between academia and society.

KTU is moving consistently and upward towards a culture of citizen science, at a sustainable pace.

Vytautas Magnus University

Implementation Process and Key Milestones

At Vytautas Magnus University (VMU), the initial discussions around the potential implementation of the BESPOC model began in November 2023, focusing on the development of a catalogue of citizen science activities at the university. However, a definitive implementation plan and timeline for the BESPOC model at VMU have not yet been established. The process to fully implement one or more BESPOC modules could range from half a year to several years, depending on various factors and decisions yet to be made.

The LibOCS Workshops and Consultancy provided by Immer Besser received a high rating of 9 out of 10 from VMU, reflecting satisfaction with the guidance and support offered. This positive feedback reflects the value of the workshops in clarifying the BESPOC model's potential impact and implementation process, despite the challenges and early stage of integration at VMU.

Institutional Changes Observed

To date, the BESPOC model's implementation process at VMU has not officially started. Consequently, specific institutional changes resulting from the BESPOC model are not observable at this stage. The preliminary discussions about introducing a catalogue for citizen science activities represent the initial step towards recognizing the importance and potential impact of structured citizen science initiatives within the university.

Impact Assessment

Given that the BESPOC model's implementation process has not commenced at VMU, reflecting on impacts, whether positive or negative, is not yet applicable. Nonetheless, the ongoing conversations around the BESPOC model highlight a positive outlook and acknowledge the model's relevance for enhancing VMU's engagement in citizen science activities. The anticipation surrounding the BESPOC model suggests a recognized need for a more structured approach to citizen science at VMU, trusting the potential benefits of its full implementation for the academic community and its connection with society.

Challenges and Future Steps

Engaging researchers in discussions about the BESPOC model has been challenging, with concerns about the potential duplication of activities. Despite these initial obstacles, the conversation about creating a catalogue of citizen science activities signifies a willingness to explore the BESPOC model's possibilities. The next immediate step in the upcoming six months includes implementing the catalogue of citizen science activities at VMU, a critical move towards formalizing the university's commitment to citizen science.

Looking forward to the next 12 and 24 months, VMU plans to engage in discussions with university research centers and institutes, fostering cooperation in citizen science projects. The BESPOC model, particularly through the framework of the Library, is envisioned as a crucial intermediary between VMU's academic departments and the public, facilitating enhanced collaboration and outreach.

Legal considerations have been identified as a specific area requiring additional support for the effective implementation of the BESPOC model at VMU. Addressing these legal aspects will be crucial for ensuring the smooth operation and expansion of citizen science activities under the BESPOC framework.

Conclusion

Vytautas Magnus University stands at the threshold of implementing the BESPOC model, with initial discussions indicating a recognition of its significance for advancing citizen science within the institution. While specific changes and impacts are yet to be realized, the positive reception to the model and the identified next steps signal a commitment to exploring and eventually integrating structured citizen science initiatives at VMU. Overcoming engagement challenges and addressing legal questions will be important as VMU progresses towards a more active role in the citizen science landscape, facilitated by the BESPOC model's comprehensive framework.

Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech)

Implementation Process and Key Milestones

At Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech), discussions regarding the BESPOC model began in October 2023, with plans to delve deeper into the model's integration within the library and Research & Administration (R&A) office in the latter half of 2024. Future steps entail mapping scientists' needs and advocating for policy reforms within the university to bolster citizen science (CS) support. The anticipated timeline for seeing tangible outcomes stretches to at least four years, given the complex nature of implementation challenges.

Key milestones thus far include establishing a liaison between the library and the Research & Administration Office, integrating CS topics into training programs, and raising awareness about the library's CS resources among researchers.

Institutional Changes Observed

Specific changes at TalTech tied directly to the BESPOC model are nascent, given the preliminary stage of its implementation. Nonetheless, an increased awareness of the library's offerings regarding CS has

been noted. This heightened visibility, while not translating into concrete CS activities yet, signifies a shift towards recognizing the library as a potential facilitator and partner in CS endeavours.

Impact Assessment

While the full implementation of the BESPOC model is still pending, initial signs of recognition have emerged, such as researchers reaching out to discuss the library's role in CS. This engagement, albeit small, is a positive indicator of the library's emerging perception as a CS collaborator.

As the process is in its infancy, measurable outcomes related to CS project initiation or participant engagement are not available. TalTech rates its current implementation level at a preliminary stage of 1 out of 10, as it's their early stages of implementing CS in general, let alone a dedicated service to support it. On the encouraging part of the scale, they received interests from their stakeholders to raise the support for citizen science.

Challenges and Future Steps

Communication has been a significant hurdle, stemming from the library's previously undefined role in CS. Addressing this challenge involves enhancing internal awareness and competency regarding CS among library staff.

Immediate actions for the next six months include internal consultations to refine the library's role in CS, ensuring the topic remains a priority, and embedding CS topics into library training to sustain and expand relevant knowledge and skills.

Looking ahead to the next 12 and 24 months, TalTech aims to foster collaboration with the University of Tartu (UT) to learn from their BESPOC implementation experiences. This partnership aspires to contribute towards establishing a national CS portal, enhancing the university's role in the CS ecosystem. Identified areas requiring further support include research communication and legal consultation to address the comprehensive needs of CS projects. TalTech highly rates the LibOCS Workshops and Consultancy provided by Immer Besser, giving a score of 9 out of 10, noting the clarity of the BESPOC model presented. As a lesson learnt, TalTech will consider tailoring their future workshop content closely to the needs and backgrounds of diverse library staff members to maximise their understanding for their own professional development, thus driving stronger engagement.

Conclusion

TalTech's efforts toward BESPOC model implementation is marked by initial awareness-raising and stakeholder engagement initiatives. Despite the challenges and the nascent stage of actual CS activities, there is a clear commitment to leveraging the BESPOC model for institutional change. As TalTech tackles the complexities of implementing BESPOC, continued learning, internal capacity building, and collaboration with external partners will be highly important in realizing the potential of CS to bridge academia and society.

Cross-institutional Analysis

The cross-institutional analysis of the BESPOC model implementation across the five LibOCS universities reveals, as expected, varied stages of adoption, challenges faced, and the impact of the model on institutional changes and citizen science (CS) activities. This analysis highlights the differences

and similarities in the approaches and outcomes of implementing the BESPOC model at these institutions.

We'd like to highlight again that the goal of this cross-institutional analysis is not to rank the BESPOC implementations across the five universities but to recognize their unique specificity and priorities. The BESPOC implementation, part of the LibOCS project, focuses on valuing collaboration over competition, encouraging mutual support, sharing practices, and engaging in meaningful dialogue. This ensures the efforts of each university in embracing citizen science are appreciated for their role in enhancing collective knowledge and academic progress.

Implementation Process and Key Milestones

- UT is in the early stages of BESPOC implementation, focusing on consultations and planning for future CS projects.
- TalTech discussed the BESPOC model, showing an understanding of its potential benefits, but has not set a specific timeline for implementation.
- UL has made considerable progress, with guidelines approved and a shift in the university's culture towards CS, marked by planning and stakeholder engagement.
- VMU has initiated discussions about the BESPOC model, particularly around creating a catalogue of CS activities, but faces challenges in launching the implementation process.
- KTU has engaged deeply with the BESPOC model, establishing partnerships, organizing workshops, and approving guidelines for CS projects.

Institutional Changes Observed

- UT and TalTech report minimal immediate institutional changes due to the nascent stage of BESPOC implementation.
- UL and KTU observe more substantial changes, including the approval of CS guidelines and the establishment of partnerships to support CS activities.
- VMU is still in the planning phase, with specific changes and impacts not yet observable.

Impact Assessment

- UT and TalTech are optimistic about the potential impacts of BESPOC, focusing on planning and stakeholder engagement.
- UL has seen a positive shift in academia-society connections, highlighted by significant stakeholder interest in CS discussions.
- VMU acknowledges the potential positive impact of BESPOC, despite being in the initial stages of discussion and planning.
- KTU reports an emerging recognition of the library as a CS support center and has initiated projects and partnerships to expand CS activities.

Challenges and Future Steps

- Common challenges across the universities include engaging stakeholders, integrating BESPOC into existing structures, and securing support for CS activities.
- UT, TalTech, and VMU are focusing on further discussions, stakeholder engagement, and planning for the implementation of specific BESPOC modules.
- UL and KTU are advancing towards deeper BESPOC model integration, with UL developing a CS portal and KTU implementing approved guidelines and expanding partnerships.

Conclusion

The comparative analysis shows that while all five universities are at various stages of the BESPOC model implementation, they share common goals of enhancing CS activities and strengthening the academia-society cooperation. UL and KTU have made the most significant progress in institutional changes and stakeholder engagement, whereas UT, TalTech, and VMU are still in the early stages, focusing on planning and discussions. Common challenges include stakeholder engagement and integrating BESPOC into university structures, but there is a clear commitment across institutions to overcome these obstacles and leverage the BESPOC model for the advancement of citizen science.

Recommendations

Here are a set of recommendations for strengthening Baltic HEIs citizen science as a form of public engagement for universities. These recommendations might be useful for other universities, too. We encourage the readers of this report to make contact with our project or with its individual partners to discuss the lessons learnt, and the challenges and solutions we identified.

1. Enhance stakeholder engagement

- Develop targeted communication strategies to better engage researchers, administrators, and students, highlighting the mutual benefits of citizen science for academia and society.
- Organize interdisciplinary forums and workshops that bring together stakeholders from within and outside the university to foster collaboration and share best practices in citizen science.
- Steadily build up this kind of engagement. Getting the large variety of stakeholders on board for citizen science or academic public engagement takes time, perseverance and is a long-term commitment.

2. Expand public outreach and education

- Increase public awareness and understanding of citizen science through regular public lectures, exhibitions, and media outreach.
- Place citizen science in the larger context of public engagement activities for your organisation and connect your efforts with similar ones from your colleagues responsible for the educational programs
- Offer citizen science (participatory science) training programs for the public to enhance their scientific literacy and skills, making it easier for them to contribute to research projects.
- Actively contribute to transitioning existing communities of interest to communities of knowledge and further on, to communities of practice and showcase the added value of your university or research organisation.

3. Develop the existing or new digital platforms and systems

- Develop or enhance your existing online portals that facilitate the sharing of research projects and results, allowing for greater transparency, participation, and dissemination of knowledge. While not all your research projects are suitable for citizen science, it is important to responsibly present your ambitions and results to the larger public.
- Explore if your existing CRIS system is suitable for expanding towards a more public interface, including more interoperability with your institutional repository.
- Understand the special requirements of engaging and communicating with the public, including among others the language, the format, and the frequency of your digital communications.
- Utilise social media in a responsible way to engage broader audiences and create communities around specific research topics or projects. Support social media platforms and tools that nurture a healthy audience (e.g. filter disinformation and prevent opinion polarisation).
- Grow your audience in a way that actively supports you in identifying accounts that misleadingly present themselves as being part of (or connected to) your organisation. In return, offer curated

and trustful information through your platforms and develop engagement programmes openly available for those interested in connecting with research activities.

4. Institutionalize citizen science

- Incorporate citizen science into university curricula by developing courses or modules that cover its principles, methods, and ethics, encouraging future researchers to engage with the public.
- Establish dedicated support structures within universities, such as offices or centres for public engagement and citizen science, to provide guidance, resources, and support to projects involving public participation.
- Aim for streamlining research-related public engagement and participatory science, moving away from strategies that align with the typically short lifespan of projects and embracing long-term strategies.

5. Other recommendations for potential improvements in implementing the BESPOC Model

- Allow your BESPOC service to gain greater adaptability of the BESPOC model to fit your specific needs, cultures, and structures, enabling more tailored approaches to implementing citizen (or participatory) science.
- Adapt your service to modular implementation strategies that allow you to prioritize certain aspects of the BESPOC model based on your immediate goals and capabilities.
- Consider the detailed guidelines and resources for each BESPOC module, including case studies, templates, and best practices, to assist your researchers in the practical aspects of implementation.
- When necessary, consider external training and consultancy services, ensuring that your organisation has access to expert advice and support throughout the implementation process.
- Support the creation of a network among institutions implementing the BESPOC model (or similar) to encourage the exchange of experiences, challenges, and successes.
- Encourage collaborative projects that involve multiple institutions, leveraging the strengths and resources of each to tackle larger societal challenges through citizen science and research-related public engagement.
- Build professional connections and attract enough resources to develop comprehensive guidelines on legal and ethical issues related to citizen science, such as data privacy, intellectual property, and participant consent, to assist your research communities in navigating these complex areas.

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